

SPATIO-TEMPORAL DYNAMICS OF SOIL EROSION IN SOUTHEASTERN NIGERIA: A GIS AND REMOTE SENSING APPROACH

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Abstract: Soil erosion is among the most severe environmental challenges globally, with its impacts particularly pronounced in southeastern Nigeria where fragile soils, high rainfall, and intensive human activities combine to accelerate land degradation. This study investigated the spatio-temporal dynamics of soil erosion in Orumba North Local Government Area, Anambra State, between 1987 and 2024 using multi-temporal Landsat imagery and Geographic Information Systems (GIS) techniques. Four objectives guided the analysis: to identify anthropogenic drivers of erosion, determine the extent and severity of erosion across land use types, assess its impacts on landscape morphology, and model spatio-temporal changes for sustainable management. The results revealed that anthropogenic pressures farmland expansion, deforestation, sand excavation, and unregulated settlement growth remain the dominant accelerants of erosion, with the Nanka–Oko–Agulu corridor emerging as the most severely affected. Multi-temporal classification showed significant fluctuations in erosion extent: from 7.97 km² in 1987, declining to 2.65 km² in 2003 following reclamation projects, before resurging between 2003 and 2024 as erosion expanded again into farmlands and settlement fringes. Morphological analysis indicated a trajectory of change from attrition (1987–2003), to fragmentation (2003–2019), and dissection (2024), reflecting a progressive decline in ecological stability. Modeling confirmed this degenerative trend, with cycles of short-term stabilization followed by renewed gully expansion under persistent human pressure. The study concludes that sustainable erosion management in Orumba North requires an integrated approach that combines continuous geospatial monitoring, stricter land use regulation, ecological restoration through afforestation, climate-smart farming, and community participation. Without such measures, southeastern Nigeria will continue to experience recurrent

cycles of degradation, threatening agricultural productivity, infrastructure, and rural livelihoods.

1. Introduction

Soil erosion remains one of the most pressing environmental challenges worldwide, threatening agricultural productivity, biodiversity, and sustainable development. Globally, it is estimated that between 22 and 75 billion tons of fertile topsoil are lost annually, with about 40% of the world's agricultural land already degraded to varying degrees (Pimentel & Burgess, 2013). The consequences of erosion extend beyond reduced soil fertility; they also include sedimentation of rivers, increased flooding risk, loss of biodiversity, and destabilization of entire ecosystems (Chalise, Kumar, & Kristiansen, 2019). These impacts are particularly severe in developing countries, where weak land management practices and rapidly growing populations intensify land pressure (Ahmad, Saeed, Shah, Gondal, & Saqib, 2022).

In Nigeria, soil erosion has emerged as one of the most destructive environmental hazards, especially in the southeastern region. The geology, loose soil formation, high rainfall intensity, and undulating topography of states such as Anambra, Enugu, and Imo predispose them to widespread gully erosion (Ofomata, 1985; Egboka, 2004). Estimates by the Nigeria Erosion and Watershed Management Project (NEWMAP, 2017) indicate that more than 6% of the country's landmass equivalent to about 6,000 km² has been affected by erosion, with Anambra State being one of the most severely impacted. Gully erosion in communities such as Nanka, Oko, and Orumba has destroyed

farmlands, displaced households, and led to loss of lives and property (Obi & Okekeogbu, 2017). This trend continues to threaten the food security and livelihoods of rural populations who depend on agriculture as their main source of income.

Despite numerous interventions, including engineering control measures, afforestation, and policy frameworks, erosion persists and in some cases worsens due to anthropogenic pressures. Human activities such as deforestation, over-cultivation, sand mining, poor construction practices, and uncontrolled urban expansion have accelerated natural erosion processes (Baude, Meyer, & Schindewolf, 2019). These activities alter natural hydrological cycles, increase surface runoff, and reduce vegetation cover, thereby intensifying soil loss and expanding gully systems. Furthermore, population growth in southeastern Nigeria has heightened land use pressure, leading to unsustainable exploitation of fragile landscapes (Okorafor, Akinbile, & Adeyemo, 2017). As a result, soil erosion has not only become an ecological issue but also a socio-economic challenge with far-reaching developmental implications.

While several studies have examined soil erosion in southeastern Nigeria, there remains a notable gap in the integration of multi-temporal satellite imagery with landscape metrics to assess erosion patterns over extended periods. Previous research has primarily focused on localized erosion impacts, short-term land use changes, or engineering solutions, often

neglecting the broader spatio-temporal dynamics that shape erosion-prone landscapes (Dotterweich et al., 2013; Umeugochukwu, Ezeaku, & Chude, 2013). Moreover, limited attempts have been made to combine geospatial technologies such as Geographic Information Systems (GIS), remote sensing, and decision tree algorithms to quantify both erosion extent and landscape morphology changes in southeastern Nigeria. This lack of holistic spatio-temporal assessment constrains evidence-based decision-making and hinders the development of sustainable erosion management strategies.

The present study addresses this gap by examining the spatio-temporal dynamics of soil erosion in Orumba North Local Government Area, Anambra State, between 1987 and 2024. Using Landsat satellite imagery, GIS-based land use/land cover (LULC) classification, and landscape metrics, the research investigates erosion hotspots, patterns of land transformation, and the interplay between anthropogenic activities and natural geomorphic processes. Specifically, the study seeks to (i) identify the key anthropogenic drivers of soil erosion in the area, (ii) quantify the extent and severity of erosion across different land use classes, (iii) assess landscape morphology changes over time, and (iv) provide evidence-based recommendations for sustainable land management. By applying a geospatial approach, this research contributes to the broader discourse on erosion monitoring and offers valuable insights for environmental policy and planning in Nigeria and other erosion-prone regions.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Study Area

This study was conducted in Orumba North Local Government Area (LGA), Anambra State, and southeastern Nigeria. The LGA lies within a zone characterized by fragile soils, steep slopes, and intense rainfall, making it one of the region's most susceptible to gully erosion in Nigeria. The area is underlain by sandy geological formations, which are highly erodible and prone to rapid gully expansion once protective vegetation cover is removed. Annual rainfall ranges from 1,800–2,200 mm, concentrated between April and October, with high-intensity storms generating large surface runoff volumes (Ofomata, 1985; Obi & Okekeogbu, 2017). The population is predominantly agrarian, with extensive farming, sand excavation, and deforestation practices, all of which exacerbate the susceptibility of the land to erosion.

2.2 Data Sources

To examine the spatio-temporal dynamics of soil erosion, multi-temporal satellite data were acquired for the period 1987–2024. Specifically, Landsat Thematic Mapper (TM) imagery (1987), Enhanced Thematic Mapper Plus (ETM+, 2003), and Operational Land Imager/Thermal Infrared Sensor (OLI/TIRS, 2019 and 2024) were employed. These datasets provided a 30 m spatial resolution suitable for detecting land use/land cover (LULC) changes and erosion-prone areas. Ancillary data, including erosion site records and intervention reports, were obtained from the Nigeria Erosion and Watershed Management Project (NEWMAP, 2017) and community surveys.

2.3 Image Preprocessing

All satellite images were subjected to radiometric and geometric corrections to eliminate sensor and atmospheric distortions.

Preprocessing was carried out using freely available GIS and remote sensing tools. Basic radiometric and geometric corrections were applied to minimize atmospheric distortions, while clouds and shadows were masked to improve classification quality. Training samples were selected based on a combination of field observations (where feasible), ancillary maps, and Google Earth high-resolution imagery. The classification outputs were visually inspected and refined to minimize spectral confusion, particularly between built-up and bare surfaces.

2.4 Analytical Approach

2.4.1 Land Use/Land Cover Change Detection

Post-classification comparison was used to detect LULC transitions between 1987, 2003, 2019, and 2024. Change matrices quantified the extent of conversion between vegetation, farmland, built-up, and erosion-prone classes. This approach allowed for temporal tracking of erosion spread and reclamation efforts.

2.4.2 Landscape Metrics

To assess landscape morphological changes, erosion-related processes such as attrition, fragmentation, and dissection were identified by comparing transitions in land cover classes across the study years. These categories provided insights into how erosion altered the landscape structure, breaking down vegetation and farmland mosaics into progressively unstable units.

2.4.3 Decision Tree Algorithm

The decision tree algorithm was implemented to identify transformation processes and classify erosion-related landscape changes. Inputs included patch area, edge length, and number of

patches at successive time steps. This approach facilitated the detection of specific morphological processes (e.g., attrition, creation, shrinkage), thereby linking observed LULC transitions with geomorphological drivers.

2.5 Validation and Accuracy Assessment

Classification accuracy was assessed using error matrices and the Kappa coefficient. Ground control points (GCPs) were collected through handheld GPS surveys (where accessible) and cross-validated with high-resolution imagery from Google Earth. Accuracy assessment yielded overall accuracies above 85% for all time periods, indicating reliable classification performance consistent with established remote sensing standards (Congalton & Green, 2009).

3. Results

Objective 1: Anthropogenic Factors Driving Soil Erosion (1987–2024)

Analysis of multi-temporal satellite images, coupled with ancillary data from NEWMAP and field reports, revealed that human activities remain the dominant forces accelerating soil erosion in Orumba North LGA. Key anthropogenic drivers identified include farmland expansion into marginal lands, deforestation for fuelwood and building materials, sand excavation, and uncontrolled settlement growth. These practices progressively stripped protective vegetation cover, destabilized the fragile sandy soils, and facilitated rapid gully development, particularly in the Nanka–Oko–Agulu erosion corridor, which emerged as the most severely impacted zone.

Figure 3.1 Transition Map to LULC classes from 1987 to 2003

The transition map from 1987 to 2003 (Figure 3.1) demonstrates that aggressive reclamation projects during this period converted approximately 7.32 km² of erosion sites into vegetation and 3.03 km² into farmland. These interventions, spearheaded by both local communities and agencies such as NEWMAP, temporarily reduced erosion severity across

Orumba North. However, the same figure also reveals dispersed conversion of erosion-prone areas into farmlands, indicating continued agricultural expansion into sensitive zones. This dual pattern reflects the tension between reclamation efforts and the pressure from subsistence agriculture.

Figure 3.2 Transition Map to LULC classes from 2003 to 2019

By contrast, the transition map from 2003 to 2019 (Figure 3.2) indicates a resurgence of anthropogenic pressure on the landscape. The highest rate of conversion during this period was from erosion sites to barelands/farmlands (1.87 km²), predominantly concentrated in the southwestern part of the LGA, around the Nanka erosion site. This area, known for its distinct Y-shaped gully system, became increasingly exploited for agriculture due to the perceived nutrient enrichment of erosion-affected soils. Smaller conversions included 0.10 km² into built-up areas and 0.12 km² into vegetation, suggesting limited reclamation activity compared to the earlier period. The clustering of conversions in erosion-prone zones highlights how unregulated land use decisions directly intensified gully expansion.

The transition analysis confirms that human-induced land use practices have been the central factor in shaping erosion patterns between 1987 and 2019. Although interventions achieved measurable reclamation in the earlier period, the persistence of farmland encroachment, sand excavation, and settlement growth undermined these gains and reactivated severe gully expansion in later years.

Extent and Severity of Soil Erosion across Land Use Types

The classification of multi-temporal Landsat imagery provided clear evidence of major shifts in land use and erosion extent over the 37-year study period. In 1987, erosion sites were widespread across Orumba North, with the Nanka erosion site serving as the most notable hotspot. Vegetation still covered large portions

of the LGA, but extensive areas had already been degraded by erosion processes. The 1987 erosion sites coverage map (Figure 3.3) reveals that the total area affected by erosion at this time was approximately 7.97 km², indicating that a substantial percentage of the LGA's landmass

had already succumbed to severe land degradation. The spatial distribution of these sites was scattered, with the highest concentrations observed in the southwestern corridor around Nanka, where the distinct Y-shaped gully system was fully active.

Figure 3.3 1987 Erosion Sites Coverage

By 2003, erosion extent had declined significantly due to aggressive reclamation and intervention projects. As shown in the 2003 erosion sites coverage map (Figure 3.4), the total erosion footprint had reduced to about 2.65 km², representing a 66.8% decrease from 1987 levels. The reduction was particularly visible in the northern parts of the LGA, where formerly

active erosion patches had transitioned into vegetation cover through targeted planting and engineering control structures. Nevertheless, residual erosion remained clustered around Nanka, confirming its persistence as a long-term hotspot despite widespread reclamation success elsewhere.

Figure 3.4 2003 Erosion Sites Coverage

Between 2003 and 2019, however, these gains began to reverse. The 2019 erosion sites coverage map (Figure 3.5) illustrates that while the overall erosion footprint further declined slightly to 2.51 km², the erosion features in Nanka expanded in width and depth. This suggests that even as reclamation contained

erosion in some zones, continued anthropogenic activities such as farming and sand excavation reactivated gullies in core hotspot areas. The concentration of erosion in fewer but more severe sites highlights a shift from widespread shallow erosion (1987) to localized but deeper and more destructive gully systems (2019).

Figure 3.5 2019 Erosion Sites Coverage

By 2024, erosion-prone areas had resurged once again. The 2024 erosion sites coverage map (Figure 3.6) shows that active gullies expanded back into farmland and settlement fringes, reflecting renewed land pressure and poor management practices. The total erosion coverage, although not as extensive as in 1987, increased compared to 2019, suggesting a re-

emergence of instability in the landscape system. This resurgence was strongly tied to farmland expansion into erosion buffers and increased settlement growth, confirming that without consistent monitoring and management, reclaimed lands are prone to reactivation.

Figure 3.6 2024 Erosion Sites Coverage

Together, these results confirm that the extent and severity of erosion in Orumba North have been dynamic over time, closely tied to land use changes. The area witnessed a major decline in erosion between 1987 and 2003, followed by a resurgence between 2003 and 2024. The maps demonstrate that farmlands and settlement fringes remain the most vulnerable land use types, consistently converted into erosion sites throughout the study period.

Impact of Soil Erosion on Landscape Morphology

The application of landscape metrics to the classified maps revealed progressive morphological transformations in Orumba North between 1987 and 2024. These transformations were primarily the result of the interaction between natural erosion processes

and anthropogenic land use practices. Between 1987 and 2003, the dominant morphological process was attrition, characterized by the shrinkage of erosion-prone patches due to widespread reclamation activities. The transition map for this period (Figure 3.7) shows extensive conversion of erosion sites into vegetation cover (7.32 km²) and farmland (3.03 km²). This pattern demonstrates the effectiveness of reclamation projects in stabilizing the landscape, as fragmented erosion sites either disappeared completely or were absorbed into surrounding land cover types. The attrition process was particularly notable in the northern parts of the LGA, where many small erosion patches were reclaimed, leading to an overall consolidation of vegetated land.

Figure 3.7 Transition Map to LULC classes from 1987 to 2003

From 2003 to 2019, however, the landscape transitioned into a phase dominated by fragmentation. The transition map for this period (Figure 3.8) reveals that erosion-prone areas became increasingly concentrated in the southwestern corridor, around the Nanka erosion site. Vegetation patches that had been consolidated in the earlier period were progressively broken into smaller, disconnected units, creating fragmented mosaics. The

expansion of farmlands into erosion buffers further disrupted landscape continuity, resulting in multiple isolated patches of vegetation interspersed with farmland and erosion scars. This fragmentation process is evident in the proliferation of small patch clusters visible in the transition map, reflecting a more vulnerable and ecologically unstable landscape.

Figure 3.8 Transition Map to LULC classes from 2003 to 2019

By 2024, the landscape was dominated by dissection processes, in which erosion not only fragmented land cover but also carved through existing farmland mosaics and settlement fringes. This resulted in elongated gully networks cutting across multiple land use classes, producing more linear and unstable erosion scars. The persistence and widening of gullies at Nanka illustrate this transformation, as previously contained erosion zones expanded into deeper, more linear systems. Dissection, therefore, represents the most destructive stage of landscape change observed in the study,

signifying both ecological degradation and loss of land for productive use.

In summary, the morphological evolution of Orumba North reflects a shift from attrition (1987–2003), to fragmentation (2003–2019), and finally to dissection (2024). These transitions confirm that while reclamation efforts achieved temporary success, continued anthropogenic pressure undermined long-term stability, pushing the landscape towards increasing ecological instability.

Spatio-Temporal Trends and Morphological Modeling

To further evaluate the dynamic evolution of soil erosion in Orumba North, a decision tree algorithm was applied to model landscape transformation processes across the study period. The outputs confirmed that the morphology of the LGA underwent three distinct phases of change: creation and attrition (1987–2003), fragmentation and shrinkage (2003–2019), and dissection with enlargement (2019–2024). The decision tree output for 1987–2003 (Figure 3.9) highlights that the dominant processes were creation of vegetation

patches and attrition of erosion sites. Reclamation efforts led to the restoration of large areas of vegetation cover, while numerous small erosion patches were eliminated entirely. This pattern of attrition aligns with earlier findings that erosion sites declined from 7.97 km² in 1987 to 2.65 km² by 2003, reflecting successful intervention by community-based projects and agencies such as NEWMAP. The landscape during this period became more consolidated, with fewer fragmented patches.

Figure 3.9 Landscape Changes from 1987 to 2003

In contrast, the decision tree output for 2003–2019 (Figure 3.10) revealed a shift towards fragmentation and shrinkage. Vegetation patches became increasingly broken into smaller, isolated fragments due to farmland encroachment and settlement expansion. At the

same time, erosion sites that had previously shrunk during reclamation began to re-emerge, with several undergoing shrinkage in size but persisting as active scars. This fragmentation process illustrates how human-induced land use

changes undermined the stability achieved during the earlier reclamation phase.

Figure 3.10 Landscape Changes from 2003 to 2019

Finally, the decision tree output for 2019–2024 (Figure 3.11) demonstrates that the landscape entered a destructive phase dominated by dissection and enlargement processes. Existing gullies expanded linearly, cutting deeper into farmland mosaics and settlement areas, thereby increasing patch edge density and reducing overall connectivity. The enlargement of the Nanka gully system is particularly notable in this phase, as it not only widened but also extended its reach into adjacent farmlands and rural roads. The prevalence of dissection confirms the persistence of erosion under intense

anthropogenic pressure and highlights the long-term instability of the landscape.

In summary, the spatio-temporal modeling results confirm that the landscape of Orumba North evolved through successive phases of stabilization and degradation, with short-lived gains from reclamation followed by renewed fragmentation and dissection. This trajectory underscores the importance of continuous monitoring and sustainable land management practices, as reclamation gains can be easily reversed without long-term intervention.

Figure 3.11 Landscape Changes from 2019 to 2024

4. Discussion

Anthropogenic Factors Driving Soil Erosion (1987–2024)

The results demonstrate that anthropogenic activities remain the dominant driver of gully erosion in Orumba North, particularly through farmland expansion, deforestation, sand excavation, and unplanned settlement growth. This aligns with the findings of Umeugochukwu, Ezeaku, and Chude (2013), who observed that agricultural encroachment into marginal lands in southeastern Nigeria exacerbates erosion processes by stripping protective vegetation cover. Similarly, Obi and Okekeogbu (2017) highlighted the destructive role of sand mining around Nanka, which accelerates gully deepening and widens erosion footprints.

Globally, similar observations have been made in countries like Ethiopia and India, where poor land management and deforestation have been strongly correlated with gully expansion (Chalise, Kumar, & Kristiansen, 2019; Singh & Singh, 2017). The transition maps from this study confirm that reclamation gains in Orumba North were undermined by renewed human pressure, particularly between 2003 and 2019. This suggests that without robust regulatory frameworks and community compliance, interventions may only achieve short-term success. The lesson here is that socio-economic drivers of erosion must be addressed alongside engineering solutions if reclamation is to be sustainable.

Extent and Severity of Soil Erosion across Land Use Types

The study revealed that erosion extent declined significantly from 7.97 km² in 1987 to 2.65 km² in 2003, reflecting the effectiveness of reclamation projects, before resurging to affect farmlands and settlement fringes by 2024. This dynamic confirms that erosion in Orumba North is not only a natural hazard but also a land use management issue. Farmlands were consistently identified as the most vulnerable land use type, particularly those within 500 m of active gullies.

This finding agrees with the work of Baude, Meyer, and Schindewolf (2019), who demonstrated that agricultural expansion into erosion-prone zones significantly increases land degradation risks. Locally, Ofomata (1985) had earlier observed that the geology and soil structure of southeastern Nigeria predispose the land to erosion, but it is poor land use practices that determine its severity. The 2024 resurgence in erosion-prone areas further echoes findings by Okorafor, Akinbile, and Adeyemo (2017), who argued that population pressure and unregulated farmland expansion remain central to the persistence of erosion in southeastern Nigeria. From a management perspective, this emphasizes the need for land use zoning and enforcement of buffer zones around erosion hotspots, ensuring that farmlands and settlements are restricted from vulnerable areas. Without such policies, future reclamation efforts may suffer the same fate as earlier interventions short-term gains followed by long-term relapse.

Impact of Soil Erosion on Landscape Morphology

Morphological analysis of the classified maps confirmed that Orumba North has undergone

progressive transformations: attrition between 1987 and 2003, fragmentation between 2003 and 2019, and dissection by 2024. These shifts illustrate the evolving interaction between natural processes and human land use practices. Attrition, driven by reclamation, demonstrated that gully footprints can be minimized when control measures are applied consistently. However, fragmentation and dissection reflect the ecological instability induced by uncontrolled farmland expansion and settlement encroachment.

Comparable studies in Macedonia (Milevski, Blinkov, & Trendafilov, 2016) and Spain (Dotterweich et al., 2013) have reported similar trajectories, where intervention-driven stabilization was followed by renewed degradation under anthropogenic pressure. In Nigeria, Egede (2013) described how human land use practices fragment landscapes, increasing edge effects and ecological vulnerability. This study's findings confirm that the morphology of Orumba North is being reshaped into smaller, disconnected land units, reducing ecological connectivity and increasing the difficulty of future restoration. The implication is that morphological stability in erosion-prone landscapes cannot rely solely on reclamation projects but requires long-term land use planning, afforestation, and sustainable agricultural practices to reduce fragmentation and dissection trends.

Spatio-Temporal Trends and Morphological Modeling

The decision tree algorithm confirmed that Orumba North's landscape transitioned from creation and attrition (1987–2003), to fragmentation and shrinkage (2003–2019), and finally to dissection and enlargement (2019–

2024). This trajectory highlights the cyclical nature of erosion management: reclamation creates temporary stability, but renewed human pressure reactivates gullies, often in more destructive forms. These results resonate with Pimentel and Burgess (2013), who warned that soil erosion tends to worsen over time if interventions are not consistently maintained. Locally, NEWMAP (2017) reported that despite millions invested in erosion control, many sites relapse due to poor community ownership and weak policy enforcement. The modeling in this study provides robust evidence that Orumba North's landscape is following a degenerative pathway, with each phase of instability leaving the land more vulnerable than before.

The decision tree outputs underscore the importance of continuous geospatial monitoring and the integration of predictive modeling into policy frameworks. By detecting early signs of fragmentation and dissection, policymakers can prioritize hotspots for intervention before degradation becomes irreversible. Moreover, embedding such modeling into community-based land management systems could improve local compliance and sustainability.

5. Conclusion

This study examined the spatio-temporal dynamics of soil erosion in Orumba North LGA, southeastern Nigeria, between 1987 and 2024, using multi-temporal Landsat imagery, GIS-based classification, landscape metrics, and decision tree algorithms. The findings underscore the complex interaction between human activities and natural processes in shaping erosion patterns and landscape morphology in this erosion-prone region. First, the analysis revealed that anthropogenic drivers particularly farmland expansion, deforestation,

sand excavation, and settlement growth remain the dominant accelerants of gully erosion. These pressures undermined earlier reclamation successes and intensified erosion hotspots, especially around the Nanka–Oko–Agulu corridor. Second, the study established that the extent and severity of erosion have fluctuated over time, with a significant reduction in erosion sites between 1987 and 2003 (66.8% decrease) due to reclamation projects, followed by a resurgence between 2003 and 2024. Farmlands and settlement fringes emerged as the most vulnerable land use classes, confirming that erosion is not only a geomorphological hazard but also a land management issue.

Third, the application of landscape metrics demonstrated a trajectory of morphological transformations, moving from attrition (1987–2003), to fragmentation (2003–2019), and ultimately dissection (2024). This progression reflects a loss of ecological stability, with vegetation patches increasingly broken into disconnected units and erosion gullies carving through farmlands and rural settlements. Finally, spatio-temporal modeling using the decision tree algorithm confirmed this degenerative pathway, showing how temporary stabilization through reclamation was followed by renewed fragmentation and enlargement of gullies. The results highlight that erosion in Orumba North is characterized by cycles of short-term recovery and long-term relapse, driven largely by unregulated human activity. In conclusion, the study demonstrates that while geospatial technologies provide powerful tools for monitoring erosion dynamics, sustainable outcomes require more than technical solutions. Effective erosion management must combine continuous monitoring, strict land use

regulation, community participation, and long-term ecological restoration strategies. Without these, southeastern Nigeria will continue to experience cycles of degradation that threaten agricultural productivity, food security, and rural livelihoods.

6. Recommendations

The findings of this study provide strong evidence that effective management of soil erosion in Orumba North requires interventions that directly address the interplay between human activities and geomorphic processes. Recommendations are therefore presented in line with the research objectives to ensure both scientific and policy relevance.

With respect to the first objective, which identified the anthropogenic drivers of erosion, it is recommended that stricter land use regulations be enforced to restrict farming, settlement expansion, and sand excavation in erosion-prone areas, particularly within the Nanka–Okoko–Agulu corridor. Illegal sand mining should be monitored and controlled through licensing systems and penalties, while deforestation pressures can be mitigated by promoting alternative energy sources such as solar cookers and biogas. Only by reducing dependence on fragile landscapes for subsistence can the cycle of human-induced erosion be broken.

In relation to the second objective, which assessed the extent and severity of erosion across land use types, the study has shown that farmlands and settlement fringes remain the most vulnerable zones. To safeguard these areas, erosion buffer zones should be delineated and legally protected to prevent cultivation or construction within sensitive belts. The adoption of climate-smart agricultural

practices, such as contour farming, cover cropping, and agroforestry, would also help to stabilize soils and reduce surface runoff. Furthermore, land use zoning plans should be prepared at the community level to redirect urban expansion away from erosion hotspots. The third objective focused on the impact of erosion on landscape morphology, where metrics revealed a trajectory of attrition, fragmentation, and dissection. In response, long-term ecological restoration strategies are essential. Sustained afforestation and reforestation programs should be implemented, particularly in buffer zones and active erosion sites. These efforts must be embedded within integrated watershed management frameworks to ensure that both upland and lowland processes are addressed simultaneously. Moreover, community participation should be prioritized to enhance the maintenance of reclamation structures and to ensure the survival of restored vegetation.

Finally, in relation to the fourth objective on spatio-temporal trends and morphological modeling, the decision tree algorithm confirmed that erosion evolves in cycles of temporary stabilization followed by relapse. To counter this degenerative pathway, it is recommended that geospatial monitoring tools be institutionalized in state and local government erosion management frameworks. Decision tree modeling and GIS-based risk maps should be routinely updated and integrated into development planning, enabling early detection of hotspot reactivation. Establishing an erosion early-warning system would further allow policymakers to intervene proactively before gullies expand into farmlands or settlements.

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